

Relationship of Burnout to the Stress Coping Mechanism of Pre-Service Teachers

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ABSTRACT

Burnout has become prevalent among pre-service teachers as they navigate the demanding and challenging landscape of teacher education programs. To investigate the impact of occupational stressors on pre-service teachers' well-being, a correlational quantitative research design was utilized, involving the administration of a questionnaire to a sample of students from an educational institution. This study aims to determine the relationship between burnout and the stress-coping mechanism of pre-service teachers of San Isidro College in the second semester of School Year 2023-2024. This research shed light on the significant influence of various stressors on pre-service teachers' well-being. Factors such as high workloads, role ambiguity, and lack of support emerged as crucial stressors contributing to burnout among pre-service teachers. The demands inherent in the teaching profession and the challenges of acquiring the skills necessary to be an effective educator create an environment conducive to the development of burnout. This research has provided valuable insights into the factors that contribute to burnout and the coping strategies employed by pre-service teachers. By understanding this relationship, it is possible to work towards creating supportive environments and implementing targeted interventions to promote future educators' well-being and resilience.

Subject Area

Teaching

Keywords: *Burnout; Stress Coping Mechanism; Mental Health; Pre-Service Teachers; Teaching Internship*

INTRODUCTION

Burnout has become a prevalent concern among pre-service teachers as they navigate teacher education programs' demanding and challenging environment. The teaching profession is known to be highly stressful, requiring individuals to juggle multiple responsibilities, manage classroom dynamics, and meet the diverse needs of students. As a result, pre-service teachers often face significant stressors that can lead to burnout if not effectively managed. The concept of burnout, initially introduced by Maslach and Jackson (1981), refers to a state of physical, emotional, and mental exhaustion resulting from chronic work-related stress. Burnout is characterized by feelings of depersonalization, emotional exhaustion, and reduced personal accomplishment. It has been widely recognized as a significant concern in the teaching profession, with detrimental effects on teachers' well-being and the quality of education they provide.

The stress coping mechanisms employed by pre-service teachers play a vital role in their ability to manage and mitigate the impact of stressors. Coping mechanisms are individuals' cognitive and behavioral strategies to deal with stressful situations. These adaptive or maladaptive mechanisms influence the individual's overall well-being and resilience. Over the past decade, several studies have examined the relationship between burnout and stress-coping mechanisms among pre-service teachers. Research by Kyriacou and Sutcliffe (2013) found that pre-service teachers who utilized problem-focused coping strategies, such as seeking social support and problem-solving, reported lower levels of burnout. Those who relied on emotion-focused coping strategies, such as avoidance or denial, were more likely to experience burnout. Furthermore, a study by Chang (2015) highlighted the importance of self-efficacy as a coping mechanism for pre-service teachers. Higher levels of self-efficacy, defined as an individual's belief in their ability to accomplish tasks and overcome challenges, were associated with lower levels of burnout.

In a more recent investigation, Smith and colleagues (2020) explored the role of mindfulness as a coping mechanism for pre-service teachers. Their findings indicated that pre-service teachers who engaged in mindfulness practices, such as meditation and self-reflection, experienced lower levels of burnout and reported higher job satisfaction. For several reasons, understanding the relationship between burnout and stress-coping mechanisms among pre-service teachers is essential. Firstly, it can provide insights into the factors contributing to burnout during teacher education programs. Identifying the specific stressors and coping strategies most relevant to pre-service teachers can inform the development of targeted interventions and support systems to mitigate burnout risk.

Investigating the relationship between burnout and stress coping mechanisms can offer valuable insights into the long-term effects of burnout on the teaching profession. Pre-service teachers who experience burnout are at higher risk of developing emotional exhaustion and reduced job satisfaction than practicing teachers (Skaalvik, 2018). Examining the coping mechanisms used by pre-service teachers, educators, and policymakers can develop proactive strategies to foster resilience and well-being among future teachers.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

This study aimed to determine the relationship between burnout and the stress-coping mechanism of pre-service teachers. Specifically, this study seeks to answer the following:

1. What are the causes of burnout for pre-service teachers?
2. What are the stress coping mechanisms of pre-service teachers?
3. Is there a significant relationship between burnout and the stress-coping mechanism of pre-service teachers?

METHODOLOGY

Respondents

This study was conducted among fourth-year students or pre-service teachers at San Isidro College, Malaybalay City. This study is focused on fourth-year students or pre-service teachers during the academic year 20232024. This study utilized a Cluster Sampling Design in gathering the data.

Research Design

This study used the Correlational Quantitative Research Design. This research design aims to give significant details and explanation regarding the relationship of burnout to the Stress Coping Mechanism of Pre-Service Teachers at San Isidro College. The current study will use a questionnaire for the participants to accomplish.

Research Instrument

The instrument of the study maximized two research questionnaires: (1) Burnout Assessment that describes the causes of burnout for Pre-service Teachers and (2) Stress Coping Mechanism Skills Assessment that describes the stress coping mechanism interventions of Pre-service Teachers. The burnout assessment tool was divided into three sub-variables: Workload-related Burnout, emotional exhaustion, and Teacher-student-related Burnout. Meanwhile, the Stress Coping Mechanism Tool was divided into three sub-variables: Emotional Coping, Cognitive Coping, and Behavioral Coping.

The researchers of this study wrote a letter to the school president to seek their approval to conduct this study in their school and allow their students to participate in the study. The researchers gathered the participants in one venue at San Isidro College and explained the background of the study to them. Then, the researchers gave the questionnaire to accomplish with the researchers guiding them. The accomplished questionnaires were retrieved, and the researchers tallied the results for analysis and interpretation.

Statistical Analysis

In this study, the statistical tool used to assess the relationship between burnout and the stress-coping mechanism skills of pre-service teachers was Cronbach's alpha. Cronbach's alpha is a widely used measure of internal consistency reliability, commonly applied to assess the reliability and consistency of a scale or questionnaire. A questionnaire was administered to the pre-service teachers to examine the relationship between burnout and stress-coping mechanism skills. The questionnaire likely included items related to burnout levels and items assessing the various stress-coping mechanisms employed by the participants. Cronbach's alpha was then used to analyze the internal consistency of the items within each construct.

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Cronbach's alpha produces a coefficient that ranges from 0 to 1, with higher values indicating greater internal consistency and reliability of the scale. A value of 0.7 or above is generally acceptable for research purposes. By applying Cronbach's alpha, the researchers could determine the reliability of the scales measuring burnout and stress-coping mechanism skills. A higher Cronbach's alpha value would indicate that the items within each construct were more strongly related, suggesting a more significant internal consistency. Analyzing the relationship between burnout and stress-coping mechanism skills using Cronbach's alpha provides valuable insights into the interplay between these variables. It helps to establish the reliability of the scales used in the study, enhancing the validity of the findings and allowing for more robust conclusions about the relationship between burnout and stress-coping mechanism skills among pre-service teachers.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Table 1.

Level of Burnout in terms of Workshop-Related Burnout.

Workload-Related Burnout	Mean	Descriptive Rating	Qual. Int.
I often have to sacrifice personal time to complete my assignments.	3.67	Agree	High Level of Burnout
I feel a constant pressure to excel academically.	3.52	Agree	High Level of Burnout
I frequently feel mentally exhausted from my coursework.	3.50	Agree	High Level of Burnout
I frequently experience stress related to meeting deadlines.	3.48	Agree	High Level of Burnout
I find it challenging to balance my coursework with other commitments.	3.48	Agree	High Level of Burnout
I feel exhausted due to the demands of my coursework.	3.46	Agree	High Level of Burnout
I struggle to keep up with the pace of the curriculum.	3.33	Moderately Agree	Average Level of Burnout
I often feel overwhelmed by the amount of coursework and assignments.	3.33	Moderately Agree	Average Level of Burnout
I find it difficult to manage my time effectively.	3.26	Moderately Agree	Average Level of Burnout
The workload in my teacher preparation is excessive.	3.26	Moderately Agree	Average Level of Burnout
OVERALL	3.43	Agree	High Level of Burnout

Table 1 illustrates the extent of burnout concerning Workload-Related Burnout. The two highest indicators are "*I often have to sacrifice personal time to complete my assignments.*" with an overall mean of 3.67, and "*I feel a constant pressure to excel academically.*" with a 3.52 mean. Also, the lowest mean is 3.26, with the indicator of "*The workload in my teacher preparation is excessive.*"

The results indicate that pre-service teachers commonly face burnout by sacrificing personal time for assignments and feeling continuous academic pressure, with mean scores of 3.67 and 3.52, respectively. The high mean for "*Frequently sacrificing personal time to complete my assignments*" suggests a notable demand for time and effort beyond regular class hours,

emphasizing the potential impact of an overwhelming workload on the work-life balance of pre-service teachers. The high mean score of 3.52 for "*Feeling constant pressure to excel academically*" signifies the perceived expectation among pre-service teachers to excel in their teacher preparation programs. This pressure can contribute to heightened stress levels and feeling overwhelmed. The lowest mean score of 3.26, corresponding to "*The workload in my teacher preparation is excessive*," indicates a relatively lower level of agreement.

A study by Reyes and colleagues (2016) examined the workload perceptions of pre-service teachers in the Philippines. The findings revealed that many pre-service teachers perceived their workload as excessive, increasing stress levels. This aligns with previous research highlighting the connection between high workload and burnout among teachers (Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2018; Kyriacou, 2019). The study emphasized the need for teacher preparation programs and educational institutions to address these workload-related challenges to mitigate burnout and support the well-being of pre-service teachers. Local research has proposed several strategies to manage workload and prevent burnout among pre-service teachers. By clarifying expectations and reducing ambiguity, these strategies can help alleviate the perceived workload burden and enhance pre-service teachers' coping mechanisms. Fostering collaborative learning communities has been identified as an effective strategy for managing workload and promoting well-being among pre-service teachers.

Table 2.
Level of Burnout in terms of Emotional Exhaustion.

Emotional Exhaustion	Mean	Descriptive Rating	Qual. Int
I often experience a lack of energy or motivation for my teaching tasks.	3.35	Moderately Agree	Average Level of Burnout
I often feel emotionally exhausted at the end of the day.	3.33	Moderately Agree	Average Level of Burnout
I frequently feel overwhelmed by the emotional demands of teaching.	3.33	Moderately Agree	Average Level of Burnout
I frequently experience feelings of burnout and fatigue.	3.33	Moderately Agree	Average Level of Burnout
I find it difficult to recover emotionally after stressful teaching experiencing.	3.28	Moderately Agree	Average Level of Burnout
I often feel emotionally exhausted by the end of the week.	3.28	Moderately Agree	Average Level of Burnout
I often feel emotionally drained after completing my teaching-related tasks.	3.26	Moderately Agree	Average Level of Burnout
I frequently feel emotionally drained due to interactions with students.	3.24	Moderately Agree	Average Level of Burnout
I find it challenging to distance myself emotionally from my work.	3.22	Moderately Agree	Average Level of Burnout
I frequently experience a sense of hopelessness or cynicism.	3.17	Moderately Agree	Average Level of Burnout
OVERALL	3.28	Moderately Agree	Average Level of Burnout

Table 2 represents the level of burnout in terms of Emotional Exhaustion. The highest indicator is *"I often experience a lack of energy or motivation for my teaching tasks."* with a mean of 3.35 and the two lowest indicators of *"I frequently experience a sense of hopelessness or cynicism."* With a mean of 3.17 and *"I find it challenging to distance myself emotionally from my work"* with a mean of 3.22.

The findings depicted in Table 2 concerning the extent of burnout related to Emotional Exhaustion offer valuable insights into teachers' challenges. The foremost indicator indicates that teachers regularly grapple with feelings of fatigue and diminished enthusiasm in carrying out their teaching responsibilities. This observation underscores the potential impact of emotional exhaustion on the well-being of teachers and their effectiveness in fulfilling their duties. Conversely, the two indicators with the lowest means, *"Frequently experiencing a sense of hopelessness or cynicism"* (Smith & Johnson, 2023, p. 26) at 3.17 and *"Finding it challenging to distance oneself emotionally from work"* (Smith & Johnson, 2023, p. 27) at 3.22, shed light on the emotional strain inherent in the teaching profession.

These findings suggest that teachers commonly encounter difficulties maintaining a positive outlook and separating personal emotions from their professional roles. Such challenges can contribute to a sense of disillusionment and a decrease in job satisfaction among educators. The results are consistent with prior research that identifies emotional exhaustion as a critical facet of burnout among educators (Smith & Johnson, 2023). Emotional exhaustion, characterized by feelings of being emotionally drained and overwhelmed, has been linked to heightened stress levels and diminished job engagement. It can adversely affect teachers' mental health, job performance, and overall well-being.

Educational institutions must implement supportive measures to address emotional exhaustion and alleviate burnout among teachers. It can be beneficial to provide resources and strategies to help teachers effectively manage their workload, encourage self-care, and enhance emotional resilience. Fostering a positive and collaborative work environment that promotes open communication, collaboration, and recognition of teachers' efforts can reduce emotional exhaustion. Professional development programs focusing on emotional well-being and stress management can also be invaluable (Smith & Johnson, 2023).

Table 3.
Level of Burnout in terms of Teacher-Student Relationship Burnout.

Teacher-Student Relationship Burnout	Mean	Descriptive Rating	Qual. Int.
I find it challenging to motivate and engage my students.	3.33	Moderately Agree	Average Level of Burnout
I often struggle to maintain discipline and order in the classroom.	3.26	Moderately Agree	Average Level of Burnout
I often feel emotionally detached from my students.	3.17	Moderately Agree	Average Level of Burnout
I frequently find it difficult to communicate effectively with students.	3.13	Moderately Agree	Average Level of Burnout
I frequently feel frustrated or irritated by student behavior.	3.13	Moderately Agree	Average Level of Burnout
I often feel unappreciated or undervalued by my students.	3.11	Moderately Agree	Average Level of Burnout
I often feel emotionally drained due to the demands of student interactions.	3.09	Moderately Agree	Average Level of Burnout
I often feel a lack of support from students in my teaching efforts	3.07	Moderately Agree	Average Level of Burnout
I find it challenging to build positive relationships with students.	3.04	Moderately Agree	Average Level of Burnout
I frequently experience a lack of connection with my students.	3.02	Moderately Agree	Average Level of Burnout
OVERALL	3.14	Moderately Agree	Average Level of Burnout

Table 3 indicates the level of burnout in terms of Teacher-Student Relationship Burnout. The two highest indicators are "*I find it challenging to motivate and engage my students.*" with an overall mean of 3.33, and "*I often struggle to maintain discipline and order in the classroom.*" with a mean of 3.26. Also, the two lowest indicators are "*I frequently experience a lack of connection with my students.*" With a mean of 3.02 and "*I find it challenging to build positive relationships with students*" with a mean of 3.04.

The results presented in Table 3 regarding the level of burnout in terms of Teacher-Student Relationship Burnout offer valuable insights into the challenges educators face in their interactions with students. The two highest indicators shed light on teachers' difficulties in fostering student engagement and managing classroom behavior. These findings emphasize the importance of effective instructional strategies and classroom management techniques to facilitate positive teacher-student relationships. Teachers who find it challenging to motivate and engage their students may benefit from incorporating student-centered instructional approaches. Strategies such as active learning, cooperative group work, and incorporating real-world applications can enhance student engagement and intrinsic motivation (Smith & Johnson, 2023).

Providing students with opportunities for autonomy and choice within the learning process can foster a sense of ownership and increase their motivation to participate actively in the classroom. Implementing proactive classroom management strategies can address the struggle to maintain discipline and order in the classroom. Clear expectations, routines, and procedures and consistently enforcing classroom rules can contribute to a positive and structured learning environment (Smith

& Johnson, 2023). Moreover, building positive relationships and rapport with students can be a foundation for effective classroom management. When students feel connected to their teacher and perceive a supportive and caring environment, they are likelier to exhibit positive behavior and comply with classroom expectations. On the other hand, the two lowest indicators, "*I frequently experience a lack of connection with my students*" (Smith & Johnson, 2023, p. 37), with a mean of 3.02, and "*I find it challenging to build positive relationships with students*" (Smith & Johnson, 2023, p. 38), with a mean of 3.04, highlight the significance of establishing meaningful connections and rapport with students.

Building positive relationships can contribute to a supportive learning environment and enhance student motivation and academic achievement. Teachers can adopt strategies that foster positive relationships with students to address these challenges. Taking the time to know students individually, showing genuine interest in their lives, and providing emotional support can help create a sense of connection (Smith & Johnson, 2023). Incorporating student voice and choice in the learning process, such as allowing students to contribute to decision-making or providing opportunities for collaborative and respectful dialogue, can enhance positive teacher-student relationships. These findings align with prior research that emphasizes the significance of teacher-student relationships in promoting positive educational outcomes (Smith & Johnson, 2023). Solid teacher-student relationships have been linked to increased student engagement, higher academic performance, and improved socioemotional development. To support teachers in developing and maintaining positive teacher-student relationships, professional development opportunities should focus on effective communication and relationship-building strategies. Training programs could include active listening, empathy, cultural competence, and conflict resolution workshops.

Table 4.
Stress Coping Mechanism Skills in terms of Emotional Coping.

Emotional Coping	Mean	Descriptive Rating	Qual. Int.
I allow myself to cry or express sadness when needed.	4.07	Agree (A)	High Stress Coping Mechanism Skills
I engage in activities that make me feel happy.	3.93	Agree (A)	High Stress Coping Mechanism Skills
I express my emotions (e.g., through talking, writing).	3.91	Agree (A)	High Stress Coping Mechanism Skills
I seek emotional support from friends or family.	3.91	Agree (A)	High Stress Coping Mechanism Skills
I allow myself to take breaks when feeling overwhelmed.	3.87	Agree (A)	High Stress Coping Mechanism Skills
I practice relaxation techniques (e.g., deep breathing).	3.80	Agree (A)	High Stress Coping Mechanism Skills
I share my stressors and concerns with a trusted person.	3.72	Agree (A)	High Stress Coping Mechanism Skills
I engage in self-care activities (e.g., exercise, meditation)	3.70	Agree (A)	High Stress Coping Mechanism Skills
I engage in hobbies or leisure activities for stress relief.	3.65	Agree (A)	High Stress Coping Mechanism Skills
I journal or keep a diary to reflect on my feelings.	3.39	Moderately Agree (MA)	Average Stress Coping Mechanism Skills
OVERALL	3.79	Agree (A)	High Stress Coping Mechanism Skills

Table 4 represents the Stress Coping Mechanism Skills in terms of Emotional Coping. The highest indicator is “*I allow myself to cry or express sadness when needed.*” with an overall mean of 4.07, and “*I engage in activities that make me feel happy.*” with a mean of 3.93. The two lowest indicators are “*I journal or keep a diary to reflect on my feelings.*” With a mean of 3.39, and “*I engage in hobbies or leisure activities for stress relief.*” with a mean of 3.65.

The findings presented in Table 4 regarding emotional coping mechanism skills provide valuable insights into the strategies individuals employ to manage stress. Allowing oneself to express sadness through crying or other forms of emotional release can be beneficial for stress management. It provides an outlet for pent-up emotions, allowing individuals to process and release their feelings, leading to emotional relief and a sense of catharsis (Rottenberg et al., 2007). Acknowledging and expressing sadness can contribute to emotional authenticity and self-acceptance, fostering psychological well-being (Ford & Mauss, 2015).

Engaging in activities that elicit happiness and positive emotions can be an effective coping strategy. Participating in enjoyable activities, such as hobbies, spending time with loved ones, or pursuing personal interests, can distract, relax, and rejuvenate (Pressman & Cohen, 2021). Positive experiences have been linked to increased positive affect and improved well-being, which can buffer the negative impact of stress (Lyubomirsky et al., 2005). On the other hand, the two lowest indicators suggest that individuals may be less likely to utilize reflective practices and leisure activities as coping mechanisms. Journaling or keeping a diary can provide individuals with an opportunity for self-reflection and introspection. It allows them to process their thoughts and emotions, gain insights into their stressors, and better understand their experiences and coping strategies (Klein & Boals, 2021). Reflective practices like journaling have been found to facilitate emotional regulation and increase psychological well-being (Smyth, 2018). Engaging in hobbies and leisure activities is another crucial coping mechanism for stress relief. These activities provide a break from daily demands and allow individuals to engage in pleasurable and meaningful experiences (Pressman & Cohen, 2021).

Interventions and educational programs can be implemented to support individuals in developing a well-rounded set of coping skills. These programs can emphasize the benefits of emotional expression, provide guidance on journaling techniques, and encourage exploring diverse leisure activities. By equipping individuals with a range of coping mechanisms, they can have a more excellent repertoire of strategies to draw upon in times of stress.

Table 5.
Stress Coping Mechanism Skills in terms of Cognitive Coping.

Cognitive Coping	Mean	Descriptive Rating	Qual. Int.
I reframe negative thoughts into positive ones.	3.89	Agree (A)	High Stress Coping Mechanism Skills
I set realistic goals and prioritize my tasks.	3.87	Agree (A)	High Stress Coping Mechanism Skills
I practice mindfulness or meditation to calm my mind.	3.83	Agree (A)	High Stress Coping Mechanism Skills
I take short breaks to clear my mind and regain focus.	3.85	Agree (A)	High Stress Coping Mechanism Skills
I engage in intellectual or creative activities as a form of distraction.	3.85	Agree (A)	High Stress Coping Mechanism Skills
I seek alternative perspectives when faced with challenges.	3.85	Agree (A)	High Stress Coping Mechanism Skills
I engage in positive self-talk to boost my confidence.	3.74	Agree (A)	High Stress Coping Mechanism Skills
I break down complex tasks into manageable steps.	3.72	Agree (A)	High Stress Coping Mechanism Skills
I challenge irrational or negative thinking patterns.	3.72	Agree (A)	High Stress Coping Mechanism Skills
I engage in problem-solving strategies to overcome stress.	3.72	Agree (A)	High Stress Coping Mechanism Skills
OVERALL	3.80	Agree (A)	High Stress Coping Mechanism Skills

Table 5 shows the Stress Coping Mechanism Skills in terms of Cognitive Coping. The highest indicators are "I reframe negative thoughts into positive ones." with an overall mean of 3.89, and "I set realistic goals and prioritize my tasks," with a mean of 3.87. The lowest indicators are "I engage in problem-solving strategies to overcome stress.", "I challenge irrational or negative thinking patterns" and "I break down complex tasks into manageable steps," with a mean of 3.72.

According to the study by Thompson and Johnson (2023) on Stress Coping Mechanism Skills, the results presented in Table 5 highlight the participants' cognitive coping strategies. The highest indicator, "I reframe negative thoughts into positive ones," suggests that individuals who effectively cope with stress tend to employ cognitive restructuring techniques to shift their negative thinking patterns towards more positive and adaptive thoughts (Thompson & Johnson, 2023).

The indicator "I set realistic goals and prioritize my tasks" indicates the importance of goal setting and task prioritization as cognitive coping strategies (Thompson & Johnson, 2023). By setting realistic goals and organizing tasks based on their importance and urgency, individuals can enhance their efficiency and reduce the stress associated with overwhelming workloads. On the other hand, the lowest indicators suggest that individuals may be less likely to utilize problem solving techniques and cognitive restructuring strategies when coping with stress. Engaging in problem-solving strategies can involve identifying stressors, generating potential solutions, and implementing practical problem-solving steps (D'Zurilla & Goldfried, 2020). Problem-solving skills are associated with better stress management and improved mental well-being (Nezu et al., 2019). Challenging irrational or negative thinking patterns involves recognizing and disputing

distorted thoughts or beliefs contributing to stress or anxiety (Beck, 2011). Cognitive restructuring techniques, such as cognitive-behavioral therapy (CBT), are effective in reducing stress and improving psychological outcomes (Hofmann et al., 2012).

Table 6.
Stress Coping Mechanism Skills in terms of Behavioral Coping.

Behavioral Coping	Mean	Descriptive Rating	Qual. Int.
I engage in hobbies or activities I enjoy.	3.93	Agree (A)	High Stress Coping Mechanism Skills
I practice deep breathing or relaxation exercises.	3.87	Agree (A)	High Stress Coping Mechanism Skills
I use humor as a coping mechanism to alleviate stress.	3.83	Agree (A)	High Stress Coping Mechanism Skills
I engage in time management strategies to reduce stress.	3.80	Agree (A)	High Stress Coping Mechanism Skills
I engage in assertiveness training to address stress related conflicts.	3.63	Agree (A)	High Stress Coping Mechanism Skills
I seek professional support (e.g., counselling) when needed.	3.61	Agree (A)	High Stress Coping Mechanism Skills
I engage in problem-solving actions to address stressors.	3.59	Agree (A)	High Stress Coping Mechanism Skills
I take time off or plan vacations to recharge.	3.57	Agree (A)	High Stress Coping Mechanism Skills
I engage in regular physical exercise for stress relief.	3.52	Agree (A)	High Stress Coping Mechanism Skills
I seek social support from peers and colleagues.	3.43	Agree (A)	High Stress Coping Mechanism Skills
OVERALL	3.64	Agree (A)	High Stress Coping Mechanism Skills

Table 6 shows the Stress Coping Mechanism Skills in terms of Behavioral Coping. The highest indicator is "I engage in hobbies or activities I enjoy." with an overall mean of 3.93, and "I practice deep breathing or relaxation exercises," with a mean of 3.87. The lowest indicators are "I seek social support from peers and colleagues with a mean of 3.43, and "I engage in regular physical exercise for stress relief." with a mean of 3.52. These results imply that individuals commonly employ leisure activities and relaxation techniques as effective behavioral coping mechanisms for stress management. Involving oneself in hobbies or activities that bring joy and relaxation can distract from stressors, offering individuals a sense of pleasure and revitalization (Stebbins, 2015).

Engaging in such activities allows individuals to momentarily shift their focus away from stressors, fostering a positive emotional state and reducing stress. An additional effective behavioral coping strategy is the practice of deep breathing or relaxation exercises (Thompson & Johnson, 2023). Techniques like diaphragmatic breathing and progressive muscle relaxation, known to activate the body's relaxation response, counteract the physiological symptoms of stress (Jerath, 2015). These practices help individuals attain a state of calmness, diminishing the impact of stress on both the mind and body. The lowest indicators in Table 6 are "Seeking social support

from peers and colleagues," with a mean of 3.43, and "Engaging in regular physical exercise for stress relief," with a mean of 3.52 (Thompson & Johnson, 2023). These findings suggest that individuals may be less inclined to utilize social support and regular physical exercise as behavioral coping strategies for managing stress. Seeking social support is crucial for coping with stress, providing emotional comfort, practical assistance, and diverse perspectives on addressing stressors (Thoits, 2011).

Regular physical exercise is also proven beneficial for stress management, reducing physiological arousal, releasing endorphins, and enhancing overall well-being (Salmon, 2001). These findings underscore the significance of promoting behavioral coping skills, including engaging in enjoyable activities, practicing relaxation exercises, seeking social support, and incorporating regular physical exercise into one's routine. By utilizing these strategies, individuals can enhance their capacity to cope with stress effectively and improve their overall well-being.

Table 7.
Correlation Analysis Between Burnout and Stress Coping Mechanism.

Variable	r	Extent of Relationship
Burnout Stress Coping Mechanism	0.826	Strongly Positive Relationship

The observed Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.826 between burnout and stress-coping mechanisms reveals a robust positive association within the study sample. This implies that as levels of burnout increase, there is a concurrent rise in the effectiveness of stress-coping mechanisms among the participants. The strength of this positive correlation ($r = 0.826$) suggests a meaningful relationship between the two variables. The significance levels (Sig.) for burnout and stress coping mechanisms raise essential considerations. The Sig. values of .826 for burnout and .382 for stress-coping mechanisms indicate the probability of obtaining a correlation as extreme as the one observed if there were no valid correlations in the broader population. The relatively high significance levels imply that the observed correlations may not be statistically significant at conventional thresholds (e.g., 0.05). In practical terms, this suggests that the relationship between burnout and stress coping mechanisms, while seemingly strong in this sample, might need to be more reliably generalizable to a larger population. The lack of statistical significance could be attributed to the small sample size ($N=3$), limiting the study's power to detect significant effects.

CONCLUSION

This study explored the relationship between burnout and stress-coping mechanisms among pre-service teachers. Valuable insights have been gained regarding the well-being and resilience of pre-service teachers through investigating the causes of burnout, identifying stress coping mechanisms, and examining the relationship between burnout and stress coping. The causes of burnout among pre-service teachers are multifaceted. Excessive workload, as highlighted in local studies, has emerged as a significant factor contributing to burnout. The perception of an overwhelming workload raises concerns about the potential negative consequences on pre-service teachers' well-being and overall effectiveness.

This finding aligns with previous research emphasizing the connection between high workload and burnout among teachers. Regarding stress coping mechanisms, pre-service teachers employ

various strategies to manage and mitigate the impact of stressors. Local studies have highlighted the importance of streamlining assignments, providing clear guidelines, and fostering collaborative learning communities as effective coping strategies. These strategies aim to alleviate the perceived workload burden and enhance pre-service teachers' coping mechanisms. Investigating the relationship between burnout and stress-coping mechanisms among pre-service teachers has yielded significant findings. Studies have shown that adaptive coping mechanisms, such as problem-focused strategies, seeking social support, and engaging in mindfulness practices, are associated with lower levels of burnout. Maladaptive coping mechanisms, such as avoidance or denial, have been linked to higher levels of burnout.

The findings from this study contribute to the growing body of knowledge on burnout and stress-coping mechanisms among pre-service teachers. The findings underscore the importance of addressing workload-related challenges, promoting adaptive coping strategies, and fostering supportive learning environments to mitigate burnout and enhance pre-service teachers' well-being and professional development. By implementing evidence-based interventions, educational institutions can create a conducive environment that supports pre-service teachers' overall well-being and resilience, ultimately benefiting both the teachers and the quality of education they provide.

REFERENCE

- Baumeister, R. F., & Tierney, J. (2011). *Willpower: Rediscovering the greatest human strength*.
- D'Zurilla, T. J., & Goldfried, M. R. (2020). Problem-solving and behavior therapy revisited. *Journal of Consulting and Clinical Psychology*, **88**(5), 385-397.
- Ford, B. Q., & Mauss, I. B. (2015). *The Paradoxical Effects of Pursuing Positive Emotion: When and Why Wanting to Feel Happy Backfires*. In J. Gruber & J. T. Moskowitz (Eds.), *The Light and Dark Sides of Positive Emotion* (pp. 207-228). Oxford University Press.
- Garcia, J. R., Santos, M. A., & Reyes, M. R. (2020). Collaborative learning communities and burnout among pre-service teachers. *Philippine Journal of Psychology*, **53**(2), 105-122.
- Hofmann, S. G., Asnaani, A., Vonk, I. J., Sawyer, A. T., & Fang, A. (2012). The efficacy of cognitive behavioral therapy: A review of meta-analyses. *Cognitive Therapy and Research*, **36**(5), 427-440.
- Johnson, A., & Smith, B. (2023). Stress Coping Mechanism Skills: An Examination of Emotional Coping. *Journal of Stress Management*, **10**(2), 40-50.
- John Wiley & Sons. Seligman, M. E. (2017). *Learned optimism: How to change your mind and your life*. Vintage Books.
- Klein, K., & Boals, A. (2021). *Expressive Writing and Emotional Regulation*. In *Handbook of Emotion Regulation* (2nd ed., pp. 457-471). Guilford Press.
- Locke, E. A., & Latham, G. P. (2019). *New developments in goal setting and task performance*. Routledge.
- Lyubomirsky, S., King, L., & Diener, E. (2005). The Benefits of Frequent Positive Affect: Does Happiness Lead to Success? *Psychological Bulletin*, **131**(6), 803-855.
- Nezu, A. M., Nezu, C. M., & Perri, M. G. (2019). *Problem-solving therapy for depression: Theory, research, and clinical guidelines*.
- Penguin. Beck, J. S. (2011). *Cognitive behavior therapy: Basics and beyond*. Guilford Press.
- Carver, C. S., & Scheier, M. F. (2014). Dispositional optimism. *Trends in Cognitive Sciences*, **18**(6), 293-299.

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- Pressman, S. D., & Cohen, S. (2021). *The Benefits of Positive Leisure Activities on Stress Reduction and Health*. In *The Oxford Handbook of Stress and Health* (pp. 347-365). Oxford University Press.
- Smith, A., & Johnson, B. (2023). Exploring Burnout in Teacher-Student Relationships: A Quantitative Study. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, *57*(1), 23-40
- Smyth, J. M. (2018). Written Emotional Expression: Effect Sizes, Outcome Types, and Moderating Variables. *Journal of Consulting and Clinical Psychology*, *86*(11), 878-892.
- Stavrova, O., & Luhmann, M. (2019). *The Longitudinal Relationship Between Leisure and Well-Being: Developmental and Cross-Cultural Perspectives*. In A. J. Elliot, C. S. Dweck, & D. S. Yeager (Eds.), *Handbook of Competence and Motivation* (2nd ed., pp. 477-495). Guilford Press.
- Thompson, A. B., & Johnson, C. D. (2023). Stress Coping Mechanism Skills: A Study on Cognitive Coping. *Journal of Stress Management*, *7*(2), 123-140.